

The Influence of Classical Poets on the Inscriptional Poets

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1. The influence of the classical poets on the inscriptional poets was much greater than that of the Vedic or Epic poets. This is evidenced by the language, the style, the poetical technique and the numerous poetic ideas and expressions borrowed by the latter from the standard kāvyas of the former from whose study they cultivated themselves, upon which they drew and with which they tried to compete now and then. Literature being a traditional, social and developing art, it is but natural that this kind of borrowing by the new from the old has always to go on. When many of the classical poets were indebted to their great predecessors for some of their poetic ideas and conventions e.g., Patanjali and Jaimini to Yāska, Kālidāsa to Vyāsa, Vālmiki, Kauṭalya, Vātsyāyana, Bhāsa and Aśvaghoṣa; Bhāravi to Kālidāsa; Māgha to Kālidāsa, Daṇḍin and Bhāravi; Sriharsha to Bhāravi and Māgha, it is no wonder that the inscriptional poets imitated them in all possible ways. Even Aśvaghoṣa and the earlier Buddhist authors were influenced by the Rāmāyaṇa. (See *J.R.A.S.B.* N. S. 23 (1927), p. 345). For a critical study of literature the mutual influence of authors and their distinctive qualities have to be considered.

Passages from some of the well-known classical Sanskrit works were bodily removed and utilized by the inscriptional poets particularly in the invocatory verses of the inscriptions. What a great influence the classical poets like Vālmiki, Kālidāsa, Bāṇa, Daṇḍin, Bhāravi and Subandhu etc., had on the inscriptional poets is very nicely shown with the help of quotations by Dr. G. Buhler in his learned essay entitled "*Indian Inscriptions and the Antiquity of Indian Artificial Poetry*". Dr. Kielhorn has shown how the poets who composed the praśastis of the Rāshtrakūṭa kings of the Deccan were greatly indebted for their expressions to works like the

"Harshacharita" and "Kādambari" of Bāṇa and the "Vāsavadattā" of Subandhu (*E.I.* 6.242). Similarly, C. Sivaramamurti has discussed this point at some length in his publications like *Indian Epigraphy and South Indian Scripts* p. 39) *Sanskrit Literature and Art* (*M.A.S.I.* No. 73, p. 101 etc.). In fact, the works of the classical poets had considerably influenced the composition of all the later inscriptional poets.

2. Of all the classical poets Kālidāsa was the most highly recognised model before the inscriptional poets, though he was never referred to in the inscriptional or classical literature before the sixth century A.D. It may be noted that inspite of the fact that Bhāsa was a great earlier poet and was reverentially referred to by Kālidāsa in his *Mālavikāgnimitra* as a poet of established reputation and some of whose ideas are reflected in Kālidāsa's works. (See Mirashi, *Śākuntala*, p. 146) he does not seem to have been popular with the inscriptional poets as Kālidāsa had been who on epigraphical grounds can well be assigned to the fourth century A.D. Kieth (*Classical Skt. Lit.*, p. 36) thinks that Vatsabhāti, author of the Mandasore prasasti of 473 A.D., was the earliest imitator of Kālidāsa in as much as there is a great similarity between the description of the rainy season in the *praśasti* and in the *Meghadūta* and also in the *Ṛitusamhāra* which is attributed to Kālidāsa. The Haraha inscription of 555 (*E.I.* 14.115) and the Mahākūṭa pillar inscription of Mangaleśa which contain many parallel passages from the works of Kālidāsa shows that the poet Kālidāsa had become fairly famous by that time and that his works were studied and copied by people aspiring to poetic fame in the middle of the sixth century A.D. The influence of Kālidāsa's *Raghuvamśa* (6-23) on the author of the Nāgārjuni cave inscriptions of Maukhari Anantavarman of the latter half of the sixth century (*C.I.I.*, Vol. III No. 50) is quite clear. How the charm of Kālidāsa's poetry was felt even by the overseas Sanskrit writers within a short period can be seen from the Cambodia inscription of Bhavarman of the beginning of the seventh cent. which shows that he had studied the works of Kālidāsa and imitates him in a number of verses (*Raghu.* 4.49; 5.54). Ravikīrti, the well-known author of the Aihole inscription of 634 A.D., though he aspired to the fame of Kālidāsa and Bhāravi, copied verses after verses from the *Raghuvamśa* and the *Kirātārjunyam* (*E.I.* 6.3). For describing the exploits of his patron Ravikīrti undoubtedly

takes as his model the Raghudigvijaya described by Kālidāsa in his Raghuvamśa. In the inscriptions of the Maitraka king, Guhasena of Valabhi, the influence of Kālidāsa is clearly seen (*F.G.I.*, p. 166). The Nagpur inscription of the Paramaras of Malva contains a lapidary account of the military exploits of Lakshmadeva (1082-1092 A.D.) wherein the mention of saffron in association with the river Vāṅkshu (Oxus) is exactly as in Raghuvamśa (4.67; *E.I.* 2.185). In one of the Huli inscriptions of the Deccan Chalukya king Vikramāditya VI, dated 1197 A.D. (*E.I.* 18.196) the introductory stanza of the Raghuvamśa is quoted. The beautiful verse 'Saudāminyā' etc. in Kālidāsa's Meghadūta is copied in v. 6 of the Garavapadu grant of the Kakatiya king Gaṇapatideva, dated Ś. 1182 (*E.I.* 18.346). The author's style which is marked by force and fluency in some places reminds us of that of some great poets. Similarly in one of the inscriptions in Rajasthan the benedictory stanza of the Śākuntala is cited as an introductory verse (*E.I.* 11.68).

3. Gadya has always been held by the Sanskrit poets as the touchstone for judging the poetic ability of a scholar. (Vāmana, Kāvya Sū. 1.3.21). The epigraphical literature may be said to be superior to the classical literature in this respect. Except the Harshacharita, Kādambari, Daśakumāracharita and the Avantisundarikathā in Sanskrit and the Kuvalayamālā in Prakrit, the classical literature does not possess any important prose compositions while they are so many in the epigraphical literature composed by various Sanskrit and Prakrit inscriptional poets in different parts of India living in different times long before Bāṇa had carried the style to perfection. The Nasik inscription of Pulumāyi in Prakrit, dated c. first cent. A.D., the Girnār inscription of Rudradāman in Sanskrit dated 150 A.D., and the Allahabad inscription of Samudragupta in Sanskrit dated c. 360 A.D., are typical early inscriptions written in prose with plurality of adjectival phrases, long compounds full of alliteration and other tricks with words and references to epic characters. The Sanskrit inscriptions are either entirely in prose, or entirely in verse or in a mixture of prose and verse. They are generally of the last kind. A major portion of the *praśasti* is in prose, the invocatory portion at the beginning and the benedictory and the imprecatory portions at the end being in verses. In the prose portion the influence of Bāṇa is seen.

In all Sanskrit literature none can equal Bāṇa in his majestic flow of language and rhythm in the construction of a sentence and in his extensive fancy exhibited by the Utprekshā. It is no wonder, therefore, that next to Kālidāsa, he had been the most popular poet whom the classical poets who succeeded him had placed before them as the model for all prose compositions. The later Western Chālukyas had so much admiration for Bāṇa that they began their records with the opening words of Bāṇa's Harshacharita. The same verse is used as an invocatory verse in the inscriptions of the Vijayanagara kings. Although a number of inscriptional poets had tried to enrich their compositions by imitating the poetic style of Bāṇa in their *praśastis* the result was sometimes very bad. The abundant use of immense compounds became an essential characteristic of the *praśastis* making them very difficult reading. In the Nidhanpur and Dubi plates of Bhāskaravarman of Assam (*E.I.* 19.118; *E.I.* 30.287) in the Anjaneri plates of Prithivichandra Bhogaśakti dated 710 (*E.I.* 25, 225) in the Gāhadwāl plates of Chandradeva (*E.I.* 14.19) and in the Rajim plates of Tivardeva (*F.G.I.* 81) the elevated style of prose is like that of Bāṇa.

In the Chendalur (Nellore Dist.) c.p. inscription of Chālukya Sarvalokāśraya, son of Vishṇuvardhana I dated 673 A.D. Sarvalokāśraya's valour and royal splendour are praised in two compound words only which fill five lines of the inscription (*E.I.* 8.28). The author of the Kaḍba c.p. inscription of the Rāshtrakūta sovereign Prabhūtavarsha or Govind III, dated 812 (*E.I.* 4.340 etc.), imitates in the prose portion of the record the style of Bāṇa. An eighth cent. inscriptional poet named Bhāskarabhaṭṭa author of the Bhandak (M.P.) Buddhist inscription states in particular that he was well versed in Sanskrit works like the Vāsavadattā and the Kādambari of Bāṇa (Bhand. list No. 1650; *I.R.A.S.* 1905, p. 624). The Śaka poet Kapila who lived at the court of the Saindhava rulers of Saurāṣṭra in the middle of the ninth cent. uses in his Ghumli inscription dated 832 A.D. long compounds, and a remarkable array of alliterative phrases (*E.I.* 26.197). The prose portion in the Parvatia plates of Vanamalavarmadeva of Pragjyotisha dated in the middle of the ninth cent. exhibits the quality called *Ojas* in a considerable degree in imitation of the style of Bāṇa (*E.I.* 29.146). The last of the introductory verses in the Reva inscription of Mahārāṇaka Kumārāpāladeva

dated v.s. 1297 and of Haripāladeva dated v.s. 1298 and of Haripāla-deva dated v.s. 1298 (I.A. 17.231 and 235) are taken from the introduction of Bāṇa's Kādambari. In such praśastis there is an abundance of similes, and metaphors and several expressions with a *double entendre* as the case with the work of Bāṇa and Subandhu.

4. With regard to the influence of the other classical poets passages from whose works are quoted by the inscriptional poets the following may be cited. Reference to the poet Bhāravi is well known from the Aihole inscription. The Revā plates of the Kalachuri king Trailokyamalla dated v.s. 1212 (E.I. 24.5) contains a quotation from Daṇḍin's Kāvyaḍarśa. The second verse in the introduction of the Daśakumāracharita is copied in a Pallava inscription of the 8th cent. at Amarāvati (S.I.I. 1.26; Kielhorn list No. 1903). Similarly the Paṭhāri inscription of the Rāshtrakūṭa king Parabala contains a verse (v. 16) which is undoubtedly a paraphrase of the verse 52 in the 19th canto of Māgha's Śiśupālavadha (E.I. 9.250). While Rājaśekhara took pride in tracing connection to Vālmiki through Bhartrameḍha and Bhavabhūti some of his verses with suitable modifications were inscribed in some inscriptions of the Kalchuri period. The invocatory verse of the Anāvāḍā inscription of the Gujarat king Sārangadeva dated v.s. 1348 is copied from the Gītagovinda of Jayadeva which casually shows that Jayadeva's works composed in the last quarter of the 12th cent. had become quasi sacred in a century of its composition in distant lands (I.A. 1912, p. 20, I.H.Q. 28.379). The ideas and expressions borrowed by the inscriptional poets are too numerous to be enumerated even if common notions are not taken into consideration. One of the poets named Achala composed two verses in praise of Nāṭyāchārya Bharata and got them inscribed on a Paṭṭadakal stone pillar in the 7th or 8th cent. (Kiel. No. 1042 I.A. 10.167).

5. One thing, however, requires to be noted that although the inscriptional poets got inspiration and borrowed ideas from their classical predecessors they had rarely mentioned them by their names and acknowledged their debt to them in simple gratitude. If they had even casually mentioned them as Bāṇa had done in the Harshacharita not only the history of epigraphical literature but that of the whole classical literature would have been considerably enlivened.

6. Another thing to be noted is that none of the great Buddhist scholars and poets like Aśvaghoṣa, Ārya Śūra or Nāgārjuna or Jain scholars and poets like Siddhasena Silanka, Abhayadeva, Śāntisūri, Devendra, Malayagiri, Haribhadra, Hemachandra, Mallisena, etc., seem to have been ever read by the inscriptional poets, not even by the Buddhist or Jain authors of inscriptions.

7. The same kind of bad taste and conventional slavery of the classical poets which we find in their literature seem to have been inherited by the inscriptional poets. We often meet with both uses and abuses of *alaṅkāra* in the epigraphical literature as in classical Sanskrit literature. Things, repellent and terrible by themselves, are sometimes conceived in images of charm and love. (V. Raghavan, Ind. Culture. 3.698). The pangs of widowed wives of the enemies of a victorious hero are one of such common themes which are found used by many classical poets e.g. Bharavi in his Kirātārjuniya. Vatsabhaṭṭi in v. 28 of his Mandsore praśasti writes thus—"Even today when the beautiful long-eyed wives of his enemies, afflicted with the severe pangs of widowhood think of him, a tremour is caused torturing their compact breasts with fear." Sūkshmaśiva in v. 4 of his Apsad inscrip. states—"Jivitagupta, who was the very moon to wither the buds of waterlilies in the form of the faces of the women of his haughty enemies." The Andhra poet Achitendravara described the Kākatīya ruler Tribhuvanamalla as the high priest giving widowhood to the women of the enemies (Hanamkonda insc. 3 Corpus insc. Telangan). The following expression of Rajguru Madan, author of the Mandhata plates and one of the greatest of inscriptional poets betrays his *anauchitya* "Rāma in battles quenched the fire of separation from his life's mistress by the water of Mandodari's tears" (E.I. 9.113). The Sanskrit poets did not understand how they were belittling the gods and goddesses whom they worshipped by attributing their own absurd sexual ideas and experiences to them. Ideas like the following in the invocatory verses of some inscriptions and classical works betray their low taste. "Vishṇu perturbed (lit. heated) by his separation from Lakshmi who was forcibly carried away by Goggaraja by his strong arms cultivated attachment for a couch in the sea." (Somayya's Surat plates of Kirtirajya, Chālukya, Pathak comm. Vol. p. 299). A Telugu poet of no mean order named Nandi states thus—When Rudradeva's cavalry rent the earth, covered the sun and darkened the world

people began to doubt whether the sun mistook the innumerable heads of enemies falling down in the battlefield for a battalion of Rahu and ran away (Corpus insc. Telangan p. 11). In their enthusiasm to show the greatness of their heroes they have shown them to be superior to the Gods. In the Bagumra prasasti dated 915 by the poets Trivikramabhaṭṭa (v. v. 16.23; E.I. 9.39) the hero is described to be superior to the god Vishnu and Parshurama. In the Citagong inscription of Kāntideva dated in the ninth cent. (E.I. 26.316) the poet means to say that although the king resembled Vishnu who had killed the demon Hiranyakasipu he did not like Vishṇu resort to fraud.

The idea however that a victorious king captivates the hearts of young ladies of enemy's cities, nay even of the enemy's families which occurs sometimes in Sanskrit and Prakrit literature as well as in epigraphical literature owes its origin to the influence of literature on chivalry so popular in ancient days. The expression describing the Vishnukunḍen king Madhavavarman in his plates as one who delighted the hearts of (or sported in company of) the best ladies in the mansions of the city of Tivara upon his great victory over king Trivaradeva of Kosala may be compared with such expressions in Rājasekahara's *Viddhaśalabhanjikā* I V. 8 and in *Gaudavaho* v. 1069 (see Mirashi-Jha Comm. Vol. p. 227).

The statement in Vijayanagar Sadāshivray's grant that the defeated kings of Anga, Vanga and Kalinga had to work as attendants on his women's apartments also smells of a bad taste and shows low vindictiveness (E.I. 4.3).

8. The inscriptional poets not only studied the classical literature but sometimes studied the inscriptions of earlier inscriptional poets. e.g. The poet Vāsula, author of the Mandsore inscription of Yaśodharman (F.G.I. No. 33) seems to have read the Allahabad praśasti of Samudragupta by the poet Harishena, since the central idea of fancying a stone pillar as an upraised arm of the earth is found in both the inscriptions and the expression sakala-vasudha etc. of Vasula closely resembles the expression sarvaprithvivijaya etc. of Harisena Chhobra, *I.H.Q.* 24.110). Similarly the later authors of the Guhila inscriptions seem to have read the earlier records of the dynasty. (*J.A.S.B.* 1909 p. 173). But it is very rarely that the classical author had ever studied even the first class praśastis about which they might not have been altogether ignorant. The following exceptional cases may how-

ever be noted. The well-known classical poet Jayadeva had read the Devpārā praśasti composed by his contemporary inscriptional poet Umāpatidhara and speaks highly of it. Two verses from the Dabhoi praśasti of Someśvaradeva of Gujerat dated 1255 A.D. are quoted in the *Sūktimuktāvali* of Jalhana, a Jain contemporary living in Devagiri in Maharashtra. Similarly some verses from the Sahasralinga praśasti of the time of Siddharāja Jayasimha of Gujerat (1094-1143) are quoted in the *Prabandhachintāmaṇi* of Merutunga (C-1305 A.D.) *J.O.I.* Baroda, I 231. Similarly the following exceptional cases may be noted where the compiler of a historical work had referred to inscriptions of earlier times. Kalhana, the author of the *Rājatarangīni*, is well-known. The author of the *Ekalingamāhātmya* had studied and utilised many old inscriptions of the royal family dated 1274, 1428 and others whose accounts he gave in his work dated c. 1450. (*E.I.* 24 (1938), p. 305).

9. Authors of Sanskrit inscriptions sometimes indulged in writing Prakrit inscriptions. But this Prakrit was a standardized language regulated by fixed laws of grammar and not like the Prakrit of the early inscriptions. The Paramara king Bhoja of Dhārā is said to have composed two Prakrit odes, each of 109 stanzas, to the tortoise incarnation of Vishnu, which were inscribed on huge stone slabs set up in the Bhoja-Śālā at Dhar. They are called Kūrmaśataka (*E.I.* 8.243). Bhoja had also composed a Prakrit poem named Kodaṇḍa Kāvya which was inscribed on stone slabs set up at Māṇḍu near Dhar, fragments of which have been discovered (*A.B.O.R.I.* 11.49). An inscribed composition wholly in Prakrit was set up in the temple of the goddess Ekavirā at Ratanpur, under the patronage of the Kalachuri king of Dakshina Kosala, whose all other inscriptions are in Sanskrit. The Sanskrit language of some Jain authors was at times influenced by Prakrit as seen from the peculiar Prakrit expressions used by them (*E.I.* 21.84).

10. Similarly authors of Sanskrit inscriptions have also sometimes composed inscriptions in one of the S. I. languages. Or it may be said that the authors of the S.I. inscriptions have also composed Sanskrit inscriptions. They were good students of Vedic, Epic and classical Sanskrit literature in all its branches and frequently borrowed ideas from them. They distinguished themselves as well in one or more S.I. languages as in Sanskrit, e.g., the

poets Achitendrasuri, Ísvarasuri, Śrīnātha etc. Śrīnātha, an Education Officer of the Reddi king was an author of both Sanskrit and Telugu inscriptions (See *E.I.* 21.271 and Corpus of Telengana inscriptions). Proper names of persons and places originally in a Dravidian language had gradually become Sanskritised. The Sanskritisation went so far that even the names of the temples originally Dravidian had acquired a Sanskrit rendering. The Bṛihadīśvara temple for instance was originally named as Periya Uḍaya Nāyanār. (*S.I.I.* Vol. III No. 62). The progress of evolution in the four S. I. languages gave rise to a distinctive S. I. literature as rich in literary works as in literary inscriptions. Alankaras not mentioned in standard Sanskrit works on Alankarasastra are found in S. I. inscriptions. Some of the inscriptions in the S.I. languages are beautiful pieces of literary art composed in the elegant Champu style, balanced with prose and verse, embellished with the figure of speech such as alliteration, simile, metaphor and echoing with pleasing sounds and melodious tunes. The S.I. inscriptions are generally very lengthy and composed with great learning and skill. The terms used in the Tamil inscriptions in special senses, are so numerous, the vocabulary is so rich, the expression is so elegant, the diction is so dignified, the flow of the verses is so easy and the narration of historical incidents is so animated that they mark them as a class by themselves in Tamil literature. How learned and gifted in poetical abilities the Kannada poets and poetesses were can be seen from an account of them given by J. J. Sharma in the Archaeological Memoir No. 13 and by P. B. Desai in Jainism in South India and from the Sasanapadyamanjari by R. Narasimhacharya and from the poetical extracts from the Ratta kings edited by Prof. Kundankar. The Vachanas of Siddharan in the Kannada language are rhythmic, elegant and simple. Similarly the Corpus of inscriptions in the Telangana districts of the former Hyderabad State edited by Dr. P. Srinivasachar gives a critical estimate of some of the Telugu poets of the Kākatiya period known from the inscriptions. Nobody seems to have done similar work giving an account of the Tamil and Malayalam poets known from inscriptions or of the poets known from the Sanskrit provincial languages like Oriya, Marathi, etc.

The short inscriptions found in Central Asia and Chinese Turkistan numbering about one thousand and dated from about

280 to 400 A.D. possess some literary importance and show that the inscriptional poets in those regions also studied the Indian literature as the inscriptional poets in India proper did. The inscriptions are written in the Brahmi script of the period, in Sanskritised Prakrit language and in the style popular in India. They are of great lexical importance in that they supply so many words of common use in Central Asia which are not found in India proper. That Sanskrit literature was regularly studied there by the people is seen from the fact that two inscriptions found at Niyā are written in Sanskrit verses in different classical metres and adorned in beautiful *alankāras*. Their themes are in the approved style of the *Nīti* literature—the impermanence of human fortune and the duty of liberality. The writer knows the rules of sandhi, long vowels, *visarga* and *virāma*. One poem opens with verses in praise of hot-air-baths of the monastery, the health giving virtues of which are celebrated with a real enthusiasm. One more inscription mentions the different branches of Sanskrit learning such as Grammar, Poetry, Astronomy, etc.

11. But Sanskrit epigraphical literature produced in South-East Asia is of much greater importance both in quality and quantity though the names of these inscriptional poets also are not known. The inscriptions show that they were highly learned as their Indian prototypes were and had made a deep study of the same subjects as the Indian poets did. The authors of the inscriptions particularly those in Cambodia, Champā, Sumātrā and Jāvā possessed intimate knowledge of the Vedas, the Upanishads, the Purāṇas, the epics, Indian mythology, philosophy, poetics and the various literary works as the Indian inscriptional poets did. They exhibit a thorough acquaintance with the different metres and the most developed rules and conventions of rhetoric and prosody. The poetic style is generally what is known as Gauḍi in India. Some of the inscriptions are very long compositions containing 50, 108, 218 and even 298 verses. The most prominent topics are eulogies of kings and details of religious endowments. Royal eulogies are generally conventional as in India. Pāṇini's grammar was carefully studied. The Sanskrit language used in their inscriptions is correct and irregularities or mistakes in grammar are very rare. It is worth noting that the king Yaśovarman who had composed a commentary on the Mahabharata and was an expert in the Horāśastra was compared

with Pāṇini. In the inscriptions of Bhavavarman and Yaśovarman references to Manu, Vātsyāyana Viśālākṣha Pravaraśena Mayūra Guṇāḍhya, Suśruta etc. are found. References to the daily recitations of the texts of the Rāmāyaṇa, Mahābhārata and the Purāṇas are found. Migration of learned persons from India is referred to in many inscriptions e.g., Śiva Soma, *guru* of King Indravarman, who had studied the Śāstras at the feet of Bhagavān Sankara. Educational institutions called Aśramas were founded in several places.

The inscriptions thus prove how thoroughly Indian learning and culture in all its aspects was imbibed in S. E. Asia from the 7th to 13th cent. A.D. India's relations with these regions particularly in the time of king Devapāladeva of Bengal and Balaputra-deva of Suvarṇadvīpa in c. 860 and of the Chola king Rajarāja and the Śailendra King Chudāmaṇivarman in the eleventh cent. were very cordial. The epigraphical literature therefore produced in these outside countries in all respects after the model of Indian epigraphical literature can very well be said to be an important section of the rich Indian epigraphical literature.

12. It is an interesting study to see where the identity of the inscriptional poets is in some way or the other traceable with known figures in available literature. The inscriptional poet Harihara, son of Pandit Mokshārka who composed the Kāntala (Saurashtra) inscription of the Gujerat Chaulakya king Arjunadeva dated V. S. 1320 may be identified with Harihara a descendant of Shri Harsha of the Naishadhiya Charita and a native of Banaras who is mentioned in the Kodinara (Saurashtra) praśasti of V. S. 1328. Similarly he seems to be the same Harihara referred to by the poet Someśvaradeva in his poems Kirtikaumudi and Surathotsava. Harihara's father Mokshārka can also be identified with Mokshāditya who composed the work, Bhimavikramavyāyoga in V. S. 1329. (Poona. Orientalist II. 228).

13. It is also interesting to see if any of the inscriptional poets had come in contact with the contemporary renowned classical poets. In this search we are greatly disappointed to find that with but one or two exceptions none of the inscriptional poets mentions of having come into contact with his contemporary classical poet and *vice a versa*. That exception is of the inscriptional poet Umāpatidhara, author of the beautiful Deopara inscription of the time of Vijayasena of Bengal. The well-known classical poet Jayadeva

who was a great friend and older contemporary of Umāpatidhara remarks in v. 4 of his Gitagovinda that Umāpati makes his words sprout (*Vāchaḥ pallavayati Umāpatidharaḥ*). Similarly Vāchaspati, author of the Bhuvaneshwar inscription and a court poet of King Harvarman of Bengal (1075-1125) describes himself as a friend of Bhaṭṭa Bhavadeva, a versatile genius who also lived at the court of the same king (J.A.S.B.N.S. 1912, Page 333).

14. Just as many poets and literary works are mentioned in classical literature in name only nothing being known of their works or of their authors many poets and many literary works mentioned in name in inscriptions have also been lost beyond recovery. The inscriptions sometimes contain references to literary works which are known by name only but which have not come down to us. Still the mention of the works is not without any importance. It is not impossible that the mention of their names and of the works, though nothing is now known of them, may lead some day to results of utmost importance. Our knowledge of Sanskrit literature would be advanced if a collection of such references of forgotten authors and of the lost works in the classical as well as in the epigraphical literature is made. Their importance for investigating the total extent of classical Sanskrit literature is only next to that of the Sanskrit anthologies which, besides mentioning the names of the authors and works now lost to us, at times furnish specimens of the literature they had produced. The Nasik plates of Dharāśraya Jayasimha dated 685 A.D. (C.I.I. IV. No. 28, v. v. 10.11) contain a reference to the work *Harapārvatīya* written by an ascetic which is not yet found. The inscriptions of the Ganga dynasty of Orissa refer to a number of scholars and poets who had lived at the court of the Ganga rulers but who are not known to us either from their literary works or from their inscriptions or even by being mentioned anywhere in the Sanskrit literature. By their mention in the inscriptions therefore we can at least assign them to a definite period and place. A Kalachuri prince named Bhimata is mentioned in a Kalachuri inscription as having written five Sanskrit plays one of which is named "*Swapnadaśānana*". But none of these works has yet been discovered. Another Kalachuri prince named Mayuraja (750.880 A.D.) is said to have written a drama called *Udāttarāghava* in imitation of Bhavabhūti. A saugata parivrāja mahāpaṇḍita Vāgīśvararakṣita, a resident of Choḍadeśa and a

disciple of Śākyarakshita of Utkaladeśa is mentioned in a c.p. inscription of the Gāhaḍvāl king Govindachandra dated 1129 A.D. (*E.I.* II. No. 3).

Some of the authors of inscriptions mention that some of their ancestors were famous poets but they are not known from any other source. Jayātman is mentioned as a great poet in the Ganjam inscription of 885 A.D. of his son Jambhala (Bhand. No. 1413 & 1414 *E.I.* 6.137). Mahādeva, a Gauḍa-kāyastha, author of the Kinsariya (Jubbulpore) inscription of V.S. 1056 speaks of his father Kalya as a poet (*E.I.* 12.59). Gangādhara who composed the Govindpur inscription of Ś. 1059 states that his father Manoratha was called Vyāsa and Neo-Kālidāsa and that his grand-father Chakrapāṇi was likened to Vālmiki and that his great grandfather was Dāmodara. The author of the Baghāri inscription of 1195 A.D. states that his father Gadādhara was named Kavichakravarti (Bhand No. 431 8.21.208). The poet Trivikrama who composed the Pāṭaṇa (E. Khandesh) praśasti of the Yadava Singhaṇa in 1207 A.D. and who styles himself as Kavichakravarti states that in his family of great Astronomers the poet Mahēśvarāchārya was born. (*E.I.* 1.341). The Atru inscription of V.S. 1314 refers to the poet Nārāyaṇa in Rajasthan who bore the epithet Mahākavi-chakravarti (Band. No. 554). Vishṇu who composed the Gwalior inscriptions of V. S. 1277 of the Tomara ruler Malayavarman (*E.I.* 30.144) calls himself to be the son of the poet Dharma. Tribhuvanapāla, author of the Ratanpur inscription of 1167 A.D. states that his father Anantapāla was a poet. (*E.I.* 26.257). One Bālakavi is mentioned in the Ghumli inscription of the poet Kapila (*E.I.* 26.197) Nothing is known of any of these poets mentioned in inscriptions of their descendants. Similarly nothing or very little is known of the poets Bhatta Bhavadeva, Nānāka, Jñānabhikṣu, etc., who are highly eulogised by other poets in their inscriptions. Similarly nothing is known of the scholar Śiva Soma, who had studied the Sāstras at the feet of Bhagavān Śaṅkara and had become Guru of the Cambodian King Indravarman.

15. One is astonished to find from a study of the inscriptions that there is hardly an inscriptional poet in the long list who is known to us from the vast Sanskrit literature by any direct or indirect reference to him. It is not known why even the more renowned poets of inscriptions are never mentioned in the Sanskrit

literature though the classical poets are sometimes respectfully mentioned in the inscriptions as in the Aihole inscription of Ravikirti, dated 634 A.D. who refers to Kālidāsa and Bhāravi respectfully.

16. Similarly it requires to be noted that none of the Sanskrit Sāhityakāras, Anthologists and Commentators has given the least consideration to the epigraphical literature and nowhere do we find any quotation from, or a reference to, an inscriptional poet while discussing or framing rules on poetics. None of the numerous commentators on Sanskrit works who not only wrote explanatory commentaries of the standard texts but also critical treatises refers to any of the inscriptional poets. It shows that the praśastis were rarely copied down and circulated among the literary world. They had their importance for the time being and though remembered by the court poets were forgotten by the general scholarly world. The only exception is found in the case of Umāpatidhara, from whose Deopārā praśasti (*E.I.* 1.305) certain verses are quoted in the anthology named *Sadūktikarṇāmṛita* of Śrīdharadāsa, a contemporary of the inscriptional poet and in two other later anthologies named *Muktāvali* and *Śārangdharapaddhati*. Similarly, *Vāchaspati*, author of the Bhuvaneśvara inscription, is mentioned in the anthology called *Sadūktikarṇāmṛita* of Śrīdharadāsa (Inscr. Bengal iii. 25) along with Bhaṭṭa Bhavadeva in the colophon of a manuscript of *Karmānuṣṭhānapaddhati*. Similarly the same inscription leads us to suppose that in exceptional cases copies of praśastis were kept evidently for the use of others. The fact that certain verses from the Deopārā praśasti are quoted in the contemporary and later anthologies as stated above shows that the praśasti was not only engraved on a stone slab at Deopārā but manuscript copies of it were used even in the life-time of Umāpatidhara and after him.

17. It may be that the inscriptional poets were not always real poets of inspiration but poets of accomplishment, though their compositions had received favours from the kings to whose courts they were attached and approbation by their influential officials. Some of them could secure such high sounding titles as Kavi, Kavīśvara Kaviśāsana, Kavichakravarti, Kavikaṇṭhavibhūṣaṇa etc. The poet Ādityadeva who composed the Enige plates of the Kalachuri king, Āhavamalla, dated Ś. 1104 calls himself Tribhuvana-

vidyā-chakravarti (Karnatak Inscriptions ii. 107). But the inscriptional poets were really practical men and tried to make up their poverty of thought by their ambition to write a grand style. It was often sufficient that they were learned in grammar (*Sabdānuśāsanavid*, (E.I. 4.156, 20.128)) and Sanskrit Lexicography and skilful in using stereotyped similes and time-worn phrases of panegyric and flattery. A person was held as a great scholar if he could perceive distinctions where none existed and silence his opponent by a brilliant display of the resources of a well-trained memory. Such poets strove more to parade their learning and vied for victory in the literary contests at royal courts. Unlike the classical works which were generally composed by the Pandits for the Pandits, the royal *praśastis* were composed by the inscriptional poets for a larger, often uneducated audience. Lively pictures of such literary diversions at courts are familiar to us in the amusing *Bhojaprabandha* and in Hemachandra's *Prabandha-chintāmani*. But if it is considered that some of the so-called classical poets also were not of a high order and were more pandits than poets, the ignoring of all the inscriptional poets by all the classical poets cannot be justified.

18. It is equally strange that the classical poets who are known to us by their works and who are known to have lived at the courts of kings or at least some of them did not compose *praśastis* in honour of their patrons to be engraved on a stone slab or a metal plate. What a sad thing it is that Kālidāsa did not find time to compose a single *praśasti* in honour of his patron whoever he was and when he lived. If he had done so, it would have solved so many questions in the history and literature of ancient India. Not a single inscription of Harsavardhana is found composed by any of his court poets Bāṇa, Mayūra, or Divākara. No eulogy of Yaśovarman of Kanauj is found written by Bhavabhūti or Vākpati who had lived at his court. Vākpati has immortalized his name by writing a beautiful Prakrit poem *Gauḍavaho* but not by composing an equally beautiful Prakrit or Sanskrit panegyric of the king. The Bengal poet Lakshmidhara, whether he lived at the court of king Bhoja of Dhārā (1010 to 1055) (*Ind. Cul.* 1.702) or at the court of king Bhojavarman of Bengal (1137-1189) (*Ind. Cul.* 2.361), is a different question, composed a *Mahākāvya* entitled *Chakrapāṇi-vijaya* (*I.A.* 1.702). But how

is it that he did not compose any of the king's inscriptions. As an exception the poet Umāpatidhara of Bengal may be mentioned who composed the beautiful Deopārā stone inscription of Vijaya-sena (A.D. 1097-1159) which is a valuable contribution to Sanskrit literature (*E.I.* 1.305).

19. But it appears more strange that the inscriptional poets, at least those who had great capacities of composing beautiful royal panegyrics, did not use their talents in composing connected poems of considerable length or prose passages or plays, or any other literary works worthy to be handed down to us as classical works. It was not impossible for them to compose *kāvya*s of many cantos and plays of several acts. The *Rājaprasasti Mahākāvya* or the *Harakeli-nāṭaka* is the only exception. Similarly, the Tirumukkudal record of the Chola king Virarājendra which is said to be the world's longest stone inscription (*E.I.* 21.220) is only an exception.

It cannot be supposed that they remained satisfied with only producing one or two *praśastis* throughout their lives. There were very few poets who had written more inscriptions than one. On the contrary some inscriptions were composed jointly by two or three persons (Bhand. List. No. 1742). The Nālandā stone inscription of Yaśovarman of the 6th cent. was written jointly by Śilachandra and Svāmidatta (*E.I.* 20.37). The Gorakhpur c.p. inscription of Jayāditya was composed jointly by Nāgadatta and his younger brother Vaidyadatta (Bhand. Lit. No. 1794). The Bilhari *praśasti* was composed by Śrinivasa Sajjana and Siruka (Bhand. List. No. 1577). The Bāra inscription was composed by Sthirarka and Nārāyaṇa (A.R. Gwalior 1925-6, p. 28). The Dhureti inscription of Chandella Trailokyamalla dated 1212 A.D. was composed by Gangadhar in collaboration with Viśveśvara (*C.I.I.* IV. 373). The Lāḍnu *praśasti* was composed by Kāmachandra Dikshita and Dhānda (Bhand. List. No. 672).

Harisena the gifted author of Samudragupta's Allahabad *praśasti* calls his piece of work a *Kāvya*. Vatsabhāti, the author of the Mandsor *praśasti*, considers his small literary piece worthy to be copied down and listened to like a great religious work. Ravikīrti, author of the Aihole *praśasti*, himself states that he had attained by his poetic skill the fame of Kālidāsa and Bhāravi. Where are his other panegyrics or works upon which

he bases his claim to be equal to Kālidāsa and Bharavi? It cannot be questioned that these poets were justified in giving big names to their literary pieces small though they are.

There is no doubt that at least some of the inscriptional poets were of a sufficiently high order. The poet Vīrasena of Pāṭaliputra who lived about the year 400 A.D. is known to us only from a small stone inscription of less than dozen lines. But even from these few lines which have survived he is seen to be a highly gifted poet at the court of an equally qualified sovereign Chandragupta II. What a sad thing it is that such poets have left no other bigger *praśastis* nor any literary work worth the name behind them! Such learned and gifted poets could not have remained satisfied with that much use of their talents throughout their lives. It cannot be supposed that there were no similar occasions to compose *praśastis* in honour of their patrons. But the fact is there that no other literary work of any of these inscriptional poets has been found.

It is impossible to believe that the *praśastis* which might have been composed by the classical poets and the plays and poems which might have been composed by the authors of inscriptional *praśastis* were either destroyed or burnt and therefore lost to us except the three or four like the Harakalināṭaka, the Lalitavigraharaja nāṭikā, the Pārijātamañjari or the Kūrmaśataka which have fortunately survived.

If their known literary works which must have been written on easily perishable material like palm or birch bark leaves have survived there was more likelihood of the survival of the inscribed works. We have therefore to suppose that the renowned poets even at the court of kings thought it derogatory to compose *praśastis* suitable for a particular occasion like the renowned poets today who are generally reluctant to compose poems on ceremonial occasions. But how are we to suppose that the great inscriptional poets did not write any poems or plays?

20. As an exception to the above statement it may be mentioned that from amongst the seven hundred inscriptional poets the following poets only have used their talents and pens for composing inscriptions as well as literary works. A majority of

them are not known from Aufretch's Catalogus Catalogorum or from any of the Anthologies like the Subhāshitaratnakosha, etc.

Umāpatidhara, Gaṅgadhara, Garuḍavāhanabhaṭṭa, Chhittapa, Trivikramabhaṭṭa, Dāmodaramiśra, Narasimhamaharshi, Nārāyaṇa, Bilhaṇa, Bhoja, Madana, Mahendravarman, Rāmachandraśūri, Lakshmidhara-Lolla, Vāchaspati, Vighararāja, Virūpāksha, Śrīnātha, Somadeva, Someśvaradeva, Svayambhu, and Halāyudha.